

Mixing Methodologies in the Study of Medieval Roofing Systems

The Case of the Veneto Region within the European Project *CaMeRoofs*

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The *CaMeRoofs* project investigates the historical development, construction techniques, and conservation of medieval church roofing systems in the Veneto hinterland. Focusing on twelve case studies dating from Late Antiquity to the Late Gothic period, the research integrates architectural history, archaeology, archaeometry, and art history to reconstruct the original configurations and transformations of wooden trusses, vaulted ceilings, and domes. Through archival research, 3D laser scanning, dendrochronological analysis, stratigraphic studies, and evaluation of pictorial and mosaic decorations, the project establishes a multidisciplinary framework for interpreting roof structures within their architectural, cultural, and technological contexts. A key objective is the creation of a digital catalogue and interactive map, providing open access to a comprehensive database of survey results, construction sequences, and restoration histories. Ultimately, *CaMeRoofs* aims to clarify the role of roofing systems in shaping medieval sacred space and to support future conservation strategies for these fragile architectural elements.

CCS CONCEPTS • **Applied computing** ~ **Arts and humanities** ~ **Architecture (buildings)** • Computing methodologies ~ Computer graphics • Information systems ~ Data management systems

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1 INTRODUCTION

Some construction systems played a paradigmatic role in shaping the architectural language of the Middle Ages. Among the most significant – though still underexplored in Italy – was the development of heterogeneous roofing systems. The shape of the roof, in fact, not only decisively influenced the internal spatiality of buildings but also played a central role in defining their external appearance. The European project *The Canopy of Heaven under a Microscope: Cataloguing Medieval Roofs (CaMeRoofs)*, coordinated by the author at the Archaeological Research Unit (ARU) of the University of Cyprus (2024-2026; supervisor: Michalis Olympios; co-supervisor: Apostolos Sarris), aims to provide critical and

multidisciplinary research data on the roofing structures of churches – such as wooden trusses, ceilings, stone vaults, domes, and more – built between the 5th and 16th centuries.

The project focuses exclusively on sacred buildings, excluding civil ones, as churches represent the best-preserved and most widespread archaeological and architectural resources since the 5th century [1]. However, many medieval roofs – both wooden and stone – were demolished and rebuilt, or at least subjected to extensive consolidation, due to their inherent fragility stemming from structural challenges and the perishability of materials. As a result, cases in which the original structures have been largely preserved are relatively rare [2]. The preliminary phase of *CaMeRoofs* (lasting two years) will therefore concentrate on a specific territory where several well-preserved examples still exist: the hinterland of the Veneto region (excluding the lagoon area for feasibility reasons). This region, unique in Italy due to its particular geographical position, has received a variety of cultural influences over the centuries – from the East, the West, and as far as Northern Europe – which contributed to the development of diverse typologies of trusses, wooden ceilings, and stone vaults [3].

Twelve monuments will be analyzed to provide an initial sampling ranging from the Early Medieval period to the Late Gothic, as listed below:

1. Sante Teuteria and Tosca at the Santi Apostoli in Verona (5th–6th century): Inscribed Greek cross plans with central cross-vaulted lantern tower and barrel vaults in the lateral arms;
2. Santa Maria Mater Domini at the Santi Felice and Fortunato in Vicenza (6th century): Inscribed Greek cross plans with central domed lantern tower and barrel vaults in the lateral arms;
3. San Prodocimo at Santa Giustina in Padua (6th century): Inscribed Greek cross plans with central domed lantern tower and barrel vaults in the lateral arms;
4. Santi Vittore and Corona in Anzù di Feltre (11th–12th century): Inscribed cross plan with groin vaults in the central and corner spans, and barrel vaults in the lateral arms;
5. Santa Corona in Vicenza (13th century): Basilica plans with quadripartite rib vaults in the main nave and side aisles;
6. San Lorenzo in Vicenza (13th-14th century): Basilica plans with quadripartite rib vaults in the main nave and side aisles;
7. Santa Anastasia in Verona (13th-15th century): Basilica plans with quadripartite rib vaults in the main nave and side aisles;
8. Cathedral of Santa Maria Matricolare in Verona (15th-16th century): Basilica plans with quadripartite rib vaults in the main nave and side aisles;
9. San Fermo in Verona (14th century): Single-hall plan with a ceiling shaped like an upturned ship's hull;
10. San Zeno in Verona (14th century): Basilica plan with a ceiling shaped like an upturned ship's hull in the main nave.
11. Baptistery of the Cathedral of Padua (13th century): Central plan with a dome.
12. Scrovegni Chapel in Padua (13th century): Single-hall plan with a barrel vault.

2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The six specific Research Objectives (ROs) of the *CaMeRoofs* project are as follows:

RO1. *Architectural history*: The first objective of the project is to determine the construction phases of the churches from their foundation to the present day. Establishing a clear chronological sequence – supported by bibliographic and archival sources, as well as direct analysis of the monuments – is an essential foundation for achieving the subsequent research objectives.

RO2. *History of restorations and current state of conservation*: The second objective is to establish a precise sequence of repair, integration, or replacement interventions carried out on the roofing systems – particularly during the 19th and

20th centuries – and to assess their current state of conservation. As previously mentioned, wooden supports are the most vulnerable elements over time and are therefore frequently subjected to restoration. These beams are especially prone to deterioration caused by rainwater infiltration, insect activity (notably xylophagous species), as shown in Figure 1, and fire damage. For these reasons, identifying the phases of structural alteration is crucial for an accurate diagnostic approach aimed at recognizing original construction elements (RO3 and RO4).

Figure 1: Verona, Cathedral of Santa Maria Matricolare. Water infiltration in the roof tiles, beams, and rafters prior to restoration (2009-2015). Source: Giancarlo Manni-“Arkitet” Studio, Verona.

RO3. *Absolute dating of the wooden components:* The third objective, building on RO2, is to establish an absolute chronology of the beams through dendrochronological analysis.

RO4. *Structure and construction phases:* The fourth objective is to investigate how the roofs are structured, understood as autonomous structural systems in which two distinct functions can ideally be identified: one oriented outward (pitched roofs) [4], and one oriented inward (ceilings or vaults) [5]. A set of data concerning the masonry and carpentry elements will be compiled, evaluating their relationship with the overall architecture. Based on this analysis, a proposed construction sequence – aligned with the findings of RO1 – will be developed to support hypotheses regarding the original configuration of the roofing systems.

RO5. *Contextualization:* After establishing the chronology of the roofing systems in relation to the construction phases and, in cases of transformation, identifying their original form (ROs 1, 3, and 4), the fifth objective is to initiate a comparative analysis between the roofing systems under examination and contemporary examples from both the Italian peninsula and continental Europe. This will help to construct a broad and interconnected framework of architectural relationships. This step – central to the overall research design – will offer insights into how roof configurations shaped medieval spatial organization, influenced the architectural conception of interior and exterior volumes, and contributed to their aesthetic and symbolic value. The heterogeneous surviving examples under study will make it possible to assess how certain structural and typological models were transmitted from one building site to another, following the movement of

craftsmen who often traveled long distances and brought with them construction knowledge that was adapted and integrated into local traditions. This will lead to a broader reflection on the technical and constructive means employed, the building practices and design sources, the influence of patrons and external factors on construction choices, as well as the role of geographical conditions, technological traditions, and the availability and processing of materials.

RO6. *Digital catalogue (dataset)*: The sixth objective is to compile all data generated from the previous research objectives into a digital database, accessible via a dedicated website. This platform will feature an interactive map through which users can access individual sections dedicated to each church. The initial interface will provide a comprehensive historical and architectural overview, including appropriate bibliographic references (RO1). The subsections will include:

1. A detailed account of restorations and the current state of conservation (RO2);
2. The results of dendrochronological analyses (RO3);
3. In-depth studies of roof structures and their construction phases, with a dedicated section for the 3D laser-scanner survey (including plans, cross-sections, longitudinal sections, as well as perspective, planimetric, and axonometric views), along with documentation of the pictorial, mosaic, and sculptural decorations of ceilings and vaults (RO4);
4. Typological classification and cultural context (RO5).

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

The research methodologies (RMs) employed in the *CaMeRoofs* project are fundamentally interdisciplinary, integrating approaches from architectural and restoration history, archaeometry, archaeology, and art history. While these methodologies originate from distinct disciplinary traditions, they are complementary and essential for conducting a holistic analysis of medieval roofing systems.

RM1. *Historical-archival methodology*: The foundation of the project lies in the bibliographic study and analysis of published sources, which are essential for reconstructing the architectural history of the churches (RO1). In the specific context of roofing systems, for example, the Cathedral of Verona represents a particularly emblematic case for examining the evolution of ecclesiastical construction processes, as its archives preserve substantial documentation related to the reconstruction of trusses and vaults initiated in 1444 [6]. As for 19th-century restorations, the project will investigate a range of unpublished sources produced by the *Commissioni Conservatrici dei Monumenti e delle Opere d'Arte* during the period spanning Italian Unification to the early 20th century. These sources are housed in the State Archives of Verona, Vicenza, Padua, and Belluno, as well as in the respective Diocesan Historical Archives. This body of material will be supplemented by documentation held by the *Soprintendenze* of Archaeology, Fine Arts and Landscape – specifically the *Soprintendenza* for the Provinces of Verona, Rovigo, and Vicenza (for the areas of Verona and Vicenza), and the *Soprintendenza* for the Metropolitan Area of Venice and the Provinces of Belluno, Padua, and Treviso (for the areas of Padua and Belluno-Feltre) –. These archives provide critical information for establishing a chronology of 20th-century restoration interventions, including technical reports, project specifications, and design documents (RO2).

RM2. *Architectural methodology*: Each roofing system will undergo a 3D laser-scanner survey, which is essential for examining with absolute precision the wooden frameworks of the attics as well as the structural components of the stone ceilings and vaults. The survey campaigns, carried out by the Architectural Survey Laboratory (LRA) of the Department of Architecture at the University of Florence (Associated Partner of the project), under the direction of Stefano Bertocci, will employ Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS) instrumentation and Structure from Motion (SfM) digital photogrammetry. These techniques, conducted both from the ground and at height, will produce a highly detailed three-dimensional dataset [7]. The primary objective of this work is to generate high-precision 2D and 3D drawings, which will allow for a comprehensive visualization of each roof system. These drawings will document the full development of the roofing

structures and capture the morphology and precise positioning of individual architectural elements both in the ceilings and stone vaults, as well as in the attics (e.g., the arrangement and configuration of the trusses, as shown in Figure 2) (RO4). Beyond offering valuable resources for the historical, artistic, and archaeological interpretation of the buildings, these graphic outputs will serve as critical documentation to support interdisciplinary analyses aimed at the conservation of the complexes [8]. They will also be essential for future monitoring, as well as for the planning of restoration and structural consolidation interventions (RO2).

Figure 2: Verona, Basilica of Santa Anastasia. Plan at attic level (2021). Source: *Soprintendenza* of Archaeology, Fine Arts, and Landscape for the Provinces of Verona, Rovigo, and Vicenza.

RM3. *Archaeometric methodology*: Dating through archaeometric analysis – specifically the dendrochronological examination of wooden structures, to be carried out by the Dendrodata Laboratory in Verona – is essential to determine whether beams that are difficult to interpret through direct inspection (or not explicitly referenced in restoration reports) are original to the construction phase or belong to later repair or reconstruction interventions (RO3). Since dendrochronology is a floating-scale dating system based on counting the annual growth rings of trees, it will be supplemented, when necessary, with radiocarbon (C-14) analysis of the wood. The integration of these two methods has already produced significant results: for instance, in the roof of San Fermo in Verona, composed primarily of larch beams from the 13th-14th centuries, thus confirming their contemporaneity with the original roof construction [9], and in the roof of the Sanctuary of Saints Vittore and Corona in Feltre, which was found to include reused larch and oak beams dating to the 13th century (Figure 3) [10].

Figure 3: Feltre (BL), Sanctuary of Saints Vittore and Corona. Wooden trusses in the attic space of the southern slope (2024). Source: Author.

RM4. *Archaeological methodology*: The intrinsic analysis of the structural fabric of the roofs, as well as the relationships between the roofing systems and the load-bearing walls of the churches, will serve to highlight discontinuities and design modifications, thereby helping to reconstruct the construction phases of the coverings (RO4). Stratigraphic analysis will be particularly valuable for examining in detail the stereometry of the stone vaults – including the shape and positioning of the stones, the use of mortars, and the presence of ribs – as well as the construction techniques of the wooden frameworks (e.g., keying, joints, and dovetailing) as shown in Figure 4. These *in situ* investigations will also enable the direct identification of restoration campaigns and structural modifications, supported by the data acquired through RO2. A particularly illustrative case is that of the roof structure of the Scrovegni Chapel in Padua, which presents a highly complex stratigraphic situation. The original 14th-century roofing consisted of beams composed of struts supported by small pillars resting on the extrados of the barrel vault. However, between 1962 and 1963, these elements were completely dismantled and replaced. During this intervention, seven metal trusses were installed, resting on a reinforced concrete perimeter frame, and a concrete screed was poured along the slopes of the roof, anchoring to the tops of the stringcourses, as illustrated in the 3D model developed by Linda Stievano (Figure 5) [11]. This intervention effectively created structural continuity between the newly added concrete roof masses and the original vault [12].

Figure 4: Vicenza, Basilica of Santa Corona. Extrados of the cross vault in the northern transept (2025). Source: Author.

Figure 5: Padua, Scrovegni Chapel. 3D models highlighting the seven metal trusses and the reinforced concrete curb installed in 1963. Source: Linda Stievano, via *Padua Thesis and Dissertation Archive* (<https://thesis.unipd.it/handle/20.500.12608/19730>).

RM5. *Historical-architectural methodology*: The integration of the roofing systems under investigation into a broader architectural context will enable the establishment of parallels between the Veneto region and neighboring areas, which are more directly linked from geographical, political, and cultural standpoints. This approach will also help define a wider framework of international relations (RO5). The Veneto hinterland constitutes a unique case for understanding how recurring or differentiated architectural forms – when interpreted within the proper historical context – are not mere secondary expressions, but rather key indicators of quality, innovation, and cultural exchange. The variety of ceilings and vaults under examination is, in this sense, highly significant. In the case of the late antique *sacella* – namely, Sante Teuteria e Tosca in Verona, Santa Maria Mater Domini in Vicenza, and San Prodocimo in Padua – the Greek cross plan with a central dome, either supported by pillars or directly anchored to the perimeter walls, and flanked by lateral barrel vaults, reveals a clear adherence to Byzantine-Ravennate models. The 14th-century wooden ceilings shaped like an upturned

ship's hull, as seen in San Fermo and San Zeno in Verona, offer striking examples of the variety and complexity of these monumental roofing systems. Although such forms flourished in the Venetian lagoon from the 13th century onward, they also find notable analogues in other parts of Europe [13]. The longitudinal basilica plans with three naves, pointed arches, and cross vaults in Santa Corona (from 1260) and San Lorenzo (from 1281) in Vicenza, as well as Santa Anastasia in Verona (from 1290), are symptomatic of French Gothic influence. This architectural language proved well-suited to the needs of the Franciscans and Dominicans, whose expanding urban presence demanded increasingly spacious ecclesiastical buildings [14]. Lastly, the barrel vault of the Scrovegni Chapel (1305), and the dome of the Baptistery of Padua (1281) reflect direct references to Roman and Late Antique prototypes. Meanwhile, the Greek cross plan with domed vaults of the Church of Saints Vittore and Corona in Feltre – completed in the second or third decade of the 12th century – constitutes a singular hybrid between Eastern and Western traditions, with explicit allusions to the typologies of the Middle Byzantine period [15].

RM6. *Historical-artistic methodology*: Pictorial decorations, where present, are integral components of ceilings and vaults and, when properly evaluated, serve as valuable *termini ante quem* for the construction of the roofing systems (RO4). Among the cases examined, for instance, the *Starry Sky* painted by Giotto in the Scrovegni Chapel allows the conclusion of the vault's construction to be securely dated to no later than 1305. Similarly, the magnificent *Paradise* fresco by Giusto de' Menabuoi adorning the dome of the Baptistery of Padua (1375-1378), and the celebratory frescoes commissioned by the Dominican friars in the vaults of Santa Anastasia in Verona (1432-1440) (Figure 6), provide critical chronological markers. In addition to frescoes, mosaics also serve as excellent chronological indicators. The symbols of the Evangelists were originally depicted in the four corner pendentives of the domed vault in the chapel of Santa Maria Mater Domini in Vicenza. Of these, only the dynamic, haloed profile of the Lion of St. Mark, with its jaws agape, survives – exemplifying a strong sense of plasticity and expression. This mosaic can be dated to the early 6th century, as confirmed by chemical, X-ray diffraction, and spectroscopic analyses conducted on the glass tesserae [16].

Figure 6: Padua, Baptistery. The Paradise fresco painted on the dome by Giusto de' Menabuoi (1375-1378). Source: Web Gallery of Art (<https://www.wga.hu/support/viewer/z.html>).

4 FUTURE PROSPECTS

A multidisciplinary analysis of medieval roofing systems focused on a relatively broad – though regionally specific – geographical area represents an innovative contribution to the landscape of Italian archaeological and architectural research [17].

The *CaMeRoofs* project aligns with this trend, while proposing an advanced methodological model capable of integrating historical data, architectural analysis, archaeometric investigation, and digital humanities as outlined in Figure 7. The multidisciplinary approach adopted allows for a move beyond the traditional typological boundaries that typically characterize studies of roofing systems – not only through the cataloguing of existing structures, but also by reconstructing their evolutionary phases, identifying the diachronic nature of transformations and restoration interventions, proposing critical contextualizations, and offering concrete tools for the preservation of these fascinating and diverse architectural testimonies.

Figure 7: Diagram illustrating the workflow of the *CaMeRoofs* project and the interaction between the Research Methodologies (RMs) and Research Objectives (ROs). Source: Author.

Contributing to the documentation and understanding of the multiple semantic layers that define roofing systems ultimately means preserving a foundational element of medieval architectural identity. It provides essential resources to ensure their appropriate conservation and engages directly with an increasingly urgent debate: the devastating fire that struck the roof of Notre-Dame Cathedral in Paris in 2019 had a profound societal impact and sparked a wide-ranging reflection on safety, restoration principles, the urban landscape, and sustainability [18].

The data will be entered into a standardized descriptive database, developed in collaboration with the DigHumanities GeoInfo Lab of the University of Cyprus. This platform will facilitate interpretation by medieval archaeologists, architectural historians, and conservation professionals, establishing itself as a valuable tool for dialogue and collaboration across disciplines and geographic regions. The creation of an interactive, continuously updatable, expandable, and open-access database represents a significant step toward more informed and shared management of historical heritage. Digital humanities, in fact, are an indispensable resource in the cataloguing, scientific analysis, and dissemination of research findings.

The ambition of *CaMeRoofs* is to establish a new standard for the study of medieval roofing systems, progressively expanding the database and fostering international comparisons. In the long term, this digital catalogue could be used on a much broader scale to identify patterns and connections – across both space and time – among examples that may appear distant or unrelated, with the ultimate goal of building an Italian and European corpus that can have tangible impacts on conservation, management, and valorization policies for medieval roofs.

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